

C- Reactive Protein: An Overview

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Introduction

Inflammation is the key response for infectious and non-infectious diseases. Response is nonspecific response irrespective of any disease condition. Acute Phase Response (APR) is the systemic response for the inflammatory condition which mainly mediated through proinflammatory hypercytokinaemia. A major property of this systemic response is dramatic change in several blood proteins which is known as Acute Phase Proteins (APP). This APP are sub-grouped in major, intermediate, minor and negative according to their kinetic properties during and after an acute phase response (Baumann and Gauldie, 1994). Acute Phase Response (APR) is an innate host defense mechanism which occurs during the early stage of infection, tissue injury or any other immunological disorders and responsible for activation of many inflammatory mediators. When there is change in concentration of some of blood proteins following APR are known as Acute Phase Proteins. C - Reactive Protein (CRP) is an APP which is secreted from liver following APR. Their secretion is mediated by cytokines produced by the inflammatory mediators during process of inflammation (Jasensky *et al.*, 2014).

Molecular Structure of CRP

C- Reactive Protein is member of the pentraxin protein family which is a phylogenetically ancient group of protein found in both vertebrate and invertebrate with a conserved structure and a calcium dependent ligand function. All pentraxins consist of one type of subunit. For CRP, five identical, non-covalently bound subunits are arranged in a planar pentagonal ring structure that can be visualized by electron microscopy. Also, the three-dimensional structure of humanoid CRP was determined, where the grooves for calcium and ligand binding can be identified. The molecular weight of canine CRP was

estimated to be in the range of 100 kDa to 155 kDa where human CRP has been observed to have affinity to a wide range of molecule and interact with several type of cell, which are the basis for wide range of hypotheses for the physiological properties of CRP (Agrawal *et al.*, 2017).

History

CRP was discovered in acute phase serum of humans as early as 1930 and has become to play a major role in human medicine. Discovery of CRP was based upon some observations on human's acute phase serum agglutinating certain members of *Pneumococcus spp.* by binding to Polysaccharide (property). In 1941, the agglutinating factor was identified as a protein where also antiserum to purified human CRP was produced in rabbits. Shortly thereafter, human CRP was crystallized and in 1950, first report of the medical applicability of CRP in monitoring rheumatic activity in rheumatic patients appeared (Shrivastava *et al.*, 2015). Canine analogue to the human CRP was investigated in canine sera in the 1960, canine CRP was isolated in 1970, and quantification was made possible in 1972 by use of specific anticanine CRP antibodies (Riley and Zontine, 1972). However, it was not really until mid of 1980 and early 1990 that thoroughly study of canine CRP was carried out. Dogs were found applicable as human acute phase models due to observed similarities between the kinetics of canine and human CRP during an APR, for which they are currently used. Since the 1990 there has been a relatively small, but currently ongoing research in the field of canine CRP, beneficial to the knowledge of both canine and human CRP.

Physiological properties of CRP

C- Reactive Protein has been conserved and present through the evolution for at least 500 million years, as its also found in the "living fossil" *Limulus polyphemus*, so it has some beneficial function. The major question is: What is the major function of CRP? A regular screening-process in the search for the physiological properties of CRP, resulting in massive amounts of information on the binding, inductive, and very interactive capacities of CRP. This been a source of further investigation and specially for further speculations on the physiological properties of CRP, resulting in a complex and unclear mixture of speculative and evidence-based statements. In serum CRP, no significant variation found due to seasonal variation, diurnal variation, age and sex, but, significant variation found in liver failure and use of some drugs (Shrivastava *et al.*, 2015).

Role of CRP in Inflammation

CRP recognizes pathogen on molecular level and eliminates it by recruiting complement system and phagocytic cells. This play's role in the clearance of injured, apoptotic and necrotic host cells by recognizing them at molecular level and contributing for restoration of normal state. It also inhibits, induced autoimmunity by scavenging altered endogenous structures and molécules. Thus, this provides

innate unspecific protection by recognition of potentially harmful foreign, altered endogenous structures and molecules (Volanakis, 2001).

Role of CRP in humans

Conditions causing major elevation of C- Reactive Protein are bacterial infections hypersensitivity complications of infections, transplantation, cancer, necrosis causing minor or no elevations inflammatory diseases like systemic lupus erythromatosus, systemic sclerosis, dermatomyositis, ulcerative colitis and cancer (Sproston and Ashworth, 2018).

Role of CRP in Atherosclerosis

Inflammation is widely considered to be an important contributing factor for pathophysiology of coronary heart disease (CHD), and the inflammatory cascade is particularly important in the atherosclerotic process. CRP emerged as one of the most important novel inflammatory markers. This, an acute phase protein is synthesized by hepatocytes in response to proinflammatory cytokines, in particular IL6. Many large-scale prospective studies demonstrated that CRP strongly and independently predicts adverse cardiovascular events, including myocardial infarction, ischemic stroke and sudden cardiac death in individuals both with and without overt CHD. CRP is believed to be a marker and a mediator of atherosclerosis and CHD. CRP plays a pivotal role in many aspects of atherogenesis including, lipids uptake by macrophage, release of proinflammatory cytokines, induces the expression of tissue factor in monocytes, promotes the endothelial dysfunction, and inhibits nitric oxide production. CRP contributes to the development and progression of atherosclerosis and thrombosis by several mechanism that induces endothelial dysfunction, leukocyte recruitment at atherosclerotic lesion, and thrombus formation through platelet activation and aggregation. mCRP is, potential regulator of signaling pathways associated with thrombosis, angiogenesis, and inflammation. Ability of CRP to bind and interact with multiple ligands underscores its implications in different steps of atherosclerosis and CVD. This contributes to atherosclerosis progression by proinflammatory effects, modulating innate immune response and activating complement system, promoting platelet activation, thrombus formation, angiogenesis, and vascular remodeling. However, CRP also act as a regulator or amplifier of the innate immune response remains to be fully elucidated in future (McFadyen, 2018).

CRP in Animals

In Canine

Concentration of serum CRP is used for routine prognostic, diagnostic, and screening purposes in a wide range of inflammatory diseases in humans, and investigations of new applications. Recent issue of CRP being an early marker or maybe even a mediator of atherothrombosis and atherosclerosis appears as one of main reasons for the marked increase in published material on human CRP. In Canine,

routine use of CRP measurement is not in practice, despite rather comprehensive knowledge of important similarities to human, regarding biochemical and physiological properties and not the least, kinetics during an acute phase response. These similarities are potential for clinical applicability within canine medicine for similar magnitude as for CRP in humans.

Bacterial Infections

Seo *et al.*, 2012 evaluated availability of CRP levels to serve as indicator for monitoring or diagnosing bacterial cystitis. Serial CRP concentrations in dogs with induced bacterial cystitis were higher than those of control groups. Viitanen *et al.*, 2014 carried out study in dogs with bacterial respiratory diseases. They found CRP as a major acute-phase protein in dogs. Serum concentrations are low in healthy animals, but increase rapidly after inflammatory stimuli. Results indicate that CRP has potential for use as an additional biomarker, especially in the diagnosis of BP.

Viral and Parasitic Infections

Kocaturk *et al.*, 2015 carried out study on serum CRP level in canines with parvoviral enteritis. Dogs with parvoviral enteritis condition had a significant increase in C- Reactive Protein compared with other healthy dogs, with an increase of higher magnitude in animals with more severe clinical signs. Carreton *et al.*, 2012 carried out study on canine heart worm disease. They stated that acute phase response in dogs with *Dirofilaria immitis*, characterized by variations of acute phase proteins (APP) is indicating inflammatory processes that could contribute to disease progression. Among them, CRP increases according to the severity of the disease and a strong correlation between pulmonary hypertension and CRP has been observed.

Surgery and postoperative care

Dabrowski *et al.*, 2009 studied changes in serum concentration of CRP, serum amyloid A component (SAA), and haptoglobin (Hp) in bitches with pyometra undergoing ovariohysterectomy that developed postoperative wound infection–related complications. **Neoplasm**

Some neoplasia also induces inflammation due to tissue invasion and destruction with release of pro-inflammatory mediators like the lymphoma and hemangiosarcoma. Dogs having localized tumors such as brain tumors or leiomyosarcoma, they do not show increased CRP (Nakamura *et al.*, 2008).

Conditions causing Minor or no Elevations

Allergic bronchitis, Atlantoaxial subluxation, Brain tumor, Diabetes mellitus, Epilepsy, Hyperadrenocorticism, Hypoadrenocorticism, Hypothyroidism, Leiomyosarcoma, and Urolithiasis (Nakamura *et al.*, 2008).

In Bovine

CRP has not been fully considered as inflammatory biomarker in cattle as compared to other APPs like SAA (serum Amyloid A) and haptoglobin. The level of CRP was found also increased during poor body condition; lactation due to stress hence it is also considering the lactation related protein. Kaya *et al.* (2016) carried out study on Swiss cows with endometritis. Results found CRP levels were higher in cows with endometritis than in that of healthy cows. Hussain *et al.* (2015) carried out study to determine CRP level in bovine obstruction of Intestine. In results, they had found significant increase in CRP and fibrinogen values.

In Equine

In Equine, release of CRP is moderate as compared to other APPs (SAA and hapatoglobin) The response in different pathological condition is observed but more study is required.

In Rabbit

Rabbit CRP level is highly inducible and responsive during the inflammatory reactions. CRP of rabbit has 70 % homology with that of CRP of humans. Normal range of CRP (serum) in Rabbit is 3.15 ± 0.8 mg/L (Sun *et al.*, 2005)

Comparison of CRP with other inflammatory markers

CRP vs. ESR

Increase in ESR is normally delayed 2 to 4 days compared to increase in CRP. ESR is not an accurate measurement of inflammation during altered RBC count.

Sensitivity and Specificity

Serum CRP level sharply follows the course and severity of inflammation. The increase in serum CRP is an effect of the increased release of cytokines from the activated inflammatory cells (Liu *et al.*, 2010).

Tests for CRP measurement

Various tests are available for CRP like;

- Slide reversed passive latex agglutination
- Sandwich ELISA
- Turbidometricimmuno Assay
- Laser nephelometric immunoassay
- Time-resolved immunofluorometric assay

Hs CRP Assay determination

During mid of 1990 a new method was developed to measure the level of CRP called Highly Sensitive CRP “hs-CRP”. Hs-CRP is not a different analyte or monomer of CRP but it is an assay that measures very low level of CRP and able to predict future cardiovascular risk.

Conclusions

CRP is expressed during APR in inflammation.

Serum CRP concentration sharply follows the course and severity of inflammation. So it surely acts as a marker of inflammation.

Its level strongly predicts future cardiovascular risk in human.

Sensitivity and specificity are superior than traditional markers of inflammation.

Preservation and Storage properties are superior than traditional markers of inflammation.

Useful for diagnosis and management of postoperative complications.

Tests for measurement of CRP are simple and reliable.

Future prospects

Role during Inflammation and CRP level estimation during healthy and disease condition.

Role of CRP in different species including wild animals.

Development of diagnostic kits for various species.

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